

ON SOME MONOTONICITY PROPERTIES OF THE ZETA FUNCTION

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ABSTRACT. Bernhard Riemann is well known as (and widely accepted to be) the pioneer of Complex Analysis. He is most particularly famous for his 1859 paper and the hypothesis that followed thereafter (for some 166 years). His paper implied that each and every complex root of the Zeta function has a real part of “0.5”.

Many Mathematicians after his time were deeply fascinated by the problem and attempted to prove it in their own ways. But, due to the passage of decades and decades of time (without any proof in sight), this problem became important enough to be included in the list of 23 notable unsolved problems of the century by David Hilbert (and later, by the Clay Math Institute).

As I got fascinated by this problem as well, I started investigating this problem from a fresh perspective. I believe that my year-long investigation has led to some interesting results. The results have been laid out in this paper.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Zeta function is an example of a class of functions known as Transcendental functions. It is a function with only one pole and infinite real and complex root points (the latter case was proven by Hardy [4]). The real root points alone are periodic. It also belongs to a class of functions known as Analytic functions. This is a function with many other special properties.

There are many definitions for the Zeta function. Some are convergent only in specific regions. Some are convergent everywhere. But, no matter the definition we take, the definition would always satisfy its functional equation (meaning $\frac{\zeta(s)}{\zeta(1-s)}$ always leads to the same ratio, no matter the definition we use — refer [Definition 8](#) for more info on the exact ratio). We can thus conclude that any property, that applies to the Zeta function, can be obtained

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from its functional equation.

My research has been primarily focused on the modulus of the Zeta function. In particular, it focuses on the square of the modulus function as the square of the modulus function does not have cusp points at its root points (which has been established in [Lemma 4](#)). This paper focuses on some results I found while investigating the claim that the square of the modulus of the Zeta function is decreasing with respect to x (whenever x belongs to $(0, 0.5)$ and $y > 14$), using different variations of the functional equation.

This paper is structured in a simple format. All the lemmas build one after another.

Some (or most) of the lemmas in this paper must be common knowledge to the subject experts. Most of the lemmas are some implications of standard results. While the standard results have been formalized, some of the implications of these standard results have not been formalized in detail. This paper focuses on formalizing those implications.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Throughout this paper, $y \geq 0$, $s = x + iy$, $s' = 1 - s$, $s \neq 1$, & γ is the Euler-Mascheroni constant. Now, some definitions that will be used throughout the paper will be established in this section.

Definition 1. The Riemann-Xi function is defined as follows (Titchmarsh and Heath-Brown 1986 [2], Section 2.1.12).

$$\xi(s) = \frac{s(s-1)\Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}\right)\zeta(s)}{2\pi^{\frac{s}{2}}} \quad (1)$$

Definition 2. The Riemann-Xi symmetric functional equation is defined as follows (Titchmarsh and Heath-Brown 1986 [2], Section 2.1.13).

$$\xi(s) = \xi(1-s) \quad (2)$$

Definition 3. Euler's identity is defined as follows.

$$e^{i\theta} = \cos(\theta) + i \sin(\theta) \quad (3)$$

Definition 4. Euler's reflection formula is defined as follows.

$$\Gamma(m)\Gamma(1-m) = \frac{\pi}{\sin(\pi m)} \quad (4)$$

Definition 5. Legendre's Duplication formula is defined as follows.

$$\Gamma(m) = \frac{[\Gamma(2m)] [\pi^{0.5}]}{[2^{2m-1}] [\Gamma(m + \frac{1}{2})]} \quad (5)$$

Definition 6. The Digamma function is defined as follows.

$$\Psi(m) = \frac{d}{dm} [\ln(\Gamma(m))] \quad (6)$$

Definition 7. An infinite sum expansion of the Digamma function is defined as follows (Olver et al. 2010 [3], Section 5.7.6).

$$\Psi(m) = -\gamma - \frac{1}{m} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{m}{n(n+m)} \right] \quad (7)$$

Definition 8. The Riemann-Zeta Analytic Continuation functional equation is defined as follows (Titchmarsh and Heath-Brown 1986 [2], Section 2.1.1).

$$\zeta(s) = \left[\frac{(2\pi)^s}{\pi} \right] \left[\sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \right] [\Gamma(1-s)] [\zeta(1-s)] \quad (8)$$

3. LEMMAS AND COROLLARIES

We now derive the supporting lemmas and corollaries in this section.

Lemma 1. $\left| \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \right|^2$ can be written as follows.

$$\left| \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \right|^2 = \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \quad (9)$$

Proof. The proof is written as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \right|^2 &= \left| \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{i\pi y}{2}\right) + \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) \sin\left(\frac{i\pi y}{2}\right) \right|^2 \\ &= \left| \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) \cosh\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) + i \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) \sinh\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right|^2 \\ &= \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) \cosh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) + \cos^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \\ &= \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 2. $\int_0^{\infty} [f(x) \sin(kx)] dx < \int_{\frac{2\pi}{k}}^{\infty} f(x) \sin(kx) dx < 0$ whenever $f(x) > 0$, $\frac{d}{dx} [f(x)] > 0$, $\mathcal{E} x$ belongs to $(0, \infty)$.

Proof. The proof is written as follows (using the transformation $u = x - \frac{\pi}{k}$).

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_0^{\infty} [f(x) \sin(kx)] dx &= \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \left[\int_{\frac{2r\pi}{k}}^{\frac{(2r+1)\pi}{k}} [f(x) \sin(kx)] dx + \int_{\frac{(2r+1)\pi}{k}}^{\frac{2(r+1)\pi}{k}} [f(x) \sin(kx)] dx \right] \\
&= \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \left[\int_{\frac{2r\pi}{k}}^{\frac{(2r+1)\pi}{k}} [f(x) \sin(kx)] dx + \int_{\frac{2r\pi}{k}}^{\frac{(2r+1)\pi}{k}} \left[f\left(u + \frac{\pi}{k}\right) \sin\left(k\left(u + \frac{\pi}{k}\right)\right) \right] du \right] \\
&= \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \left[\int_{\frac{2r\pi}{k}}^{\frac{(2r+1)\pi}{k}} [f(x) \sin(kx)] dx + \int_{\frac{2r\pi}{k}}^{\frac{(2r+1)\pi}{k}} \left[f\left(u + \frac{\pi}{k}\right) \sin(ku + \pi) \right] du \right] \\
&= \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \left[\int_{\frac{2r\pi}{k}}^{\frac{(2r+1)\pi}{k}} [f(x) \sin(kx)] dx - \int_{\frac{2r\pi}{k}}^{\frac{(2r+1)\pi}{k}} \left[f\left(x + \frac{\pi}{k}\right) \sin(kx) \right] dx \right] \\
&= \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \left[\int_{\frac{2r\pi}{k}}^{\frac{(2r+1)\pi}{k}} \left[\left[f(x) - f\left(x + \frac{\pi}{k}\right) \right] \sin(kx) \right] dx \right]
\end{aligned}$$

Since $f(x)$ is a positive, increasing function within our given constraints, $f(x) < f\left(x + \frac{\pi}{k}\right)$. Therefore, each term of this discrete infinite sum is negative and thus, the first term of this infinite sum can be considered as an upper bound for this infinite sum. Hence the lemma is proved. \square

Lemma 3. *The Riemann-Xi function can be written as follows.*

$$|\xi(s)|^2 = |\xi(x+iy)|^2 = \frac{[x^2 + y^2] [(x-1)^2 + y^2] \left[\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{x+iy}{2}\right) \right|^2 \right] [|\zeta(x+iy)|^2]}{4\pi^x} \quad (10)$$

Proof. The proof can be explained using [Definition 1](#) and [Definition 3](#). \square

Lemma 4. *At all non-trivial root points (complex root points) of the Zeta function, the following result is always true.*

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(x+iy)|^2] &= \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [|\zeta(x+iy)|^2] = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2] = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [|\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2] \\
&= |\zeta(x+iy)|^2 = |\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2 = 0
\end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Proof. It can be understood visually as the square of the modulus of the Zeta / Riemann-Xi function is always positive. Even if the modulus function leaves a sharp edge (cusp points) at the roots of the Zeta function, the square of the modulus would make it a smooth curve at root points. This lemma is thus understood that way (And it can also be established

using any definition of the Zeta / Xi function if necessary). A proof has been added in the following lines for the sake of completeness.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(x+iy)|^2] \\
&= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [[\operatorname{Re}(\zeta(x+iy))]^2 + [\operatorname{Im}(\zeta(x+iy))]^2] \\
&= 2 \left[[\operatorname{Re}(\zeta(x+iy))] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\operatorname{Re}(\zeta(x+iy))] \right] + [\operatorname{Im}(\zeta(x+iy))] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\operatorname{Im}(\zeta(x+iy))] \right] \right] \\
&= 0
\end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 5. $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2]$ and $\frac{\partial}{\partial y} [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2]$ can be written as follows.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] = -2 [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] [\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(1-x-iy))] \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] = 2 [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] [\operatorname{Im}(\Psi(1-x-iy))] \quad (13)$$

Proof. It can be proved as follows (via this principle for holomorphic / meromorphic functions $\frac{d}{ds} [f(x+iy)] = \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} = -i \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \right)$ (as the limit of a holomorphic function at a point is the same from any direction)). The following result is also used to prove the second half of this lemma.

$$\begin{aligned}
i[\Psi(1-x+iy) - \Psi(1-x-iy)] &= i[i\operatorname{Im}(\Psi(1-x+iy)) - i\operatorname{Im}(\Psi(1-x-iy))] \\
&= i[-i\operatorname{Im}(\Psi(1-x-iy)) - i\operatorname{Im}(\Psi(1-x-iy))] \\
&= 2\operatorname{Im}(\Psi(1-x-iy))
\end{aligned}$$

Let us now proceed with proving this lemma (using Schwarz' Reflection Principle).

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] \\
&= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [[\operatorname{Re}(\Gamma(1-x-iy))]^2 + [\operatorname{Im}(\Gamma(1-x-iy))]^2] \\
&= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [[\operatorname{Re}(\Gamma(1-x-iy)) + \operatorname{Im}(\Gamma(1-x-iy))] [\operatorname{Re}(\Gamma(1-x-iy)) - \operatorname{Im}(\Gamma(1-x-iy))]] \\
&= [\Gamma(1-x-iy)] \left[\left[\frac{d}{ds'} [\Gamma(1-x+iy)] \right] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [1-x+iy] \right] \right] \\
&\quad + [\Gamma(1-x+iy)] \left[\left[\frac{d}{ds'} [\Gamma(1-x-iy)] \right] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [1-x-iy] \right] \right] \\
&= - \left[[|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] \left[\frac{\frac{d}{ds'} [\Gamma(1-x+iy)]}{\Gamma(1-x+iy)} \right] + [|\Gamma(1-x+iy)|^2] \left[\frac{\frac{d}{ds'} [\Gamma(1-x-iy)]}{\Gamma(1-x-iy)} \right] \right] \\
&= - [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] [\Psi(1-x+iy) + \Psi(1-x-iy)] \\
&= -2 [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] [\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(1-x-iy))]
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, the other partial derivative is defined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] \\
&= [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] \left[\frac{\left[\frac{d}{ds'} [\Gamma(1-x+iy)] \right] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial y} [1-x+iy] \right]}{\Gamma(1-x+iy)} \right] \\
&\quad + [|\Gamma(1-x+iy)|^2] \left[\frac{\left[\frac{d}{ds'} [\Gamma(1-x-iy)] \right] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial y} [1-x-iy] \right]}{\Gamma(1-x-iy)} \right] \\
&= [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] [i\Psi(1-x+iy) - i\Psi(1-x-iy)] \\
&= 2 [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] [Im(\Psi(1-x-iy))]
\end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 6. *The real and imaginary parts of the Digamma function can be written as follows.*

$$Re(\Psi(x+iy)) = -\gamma - \frac{x}{x^2+y^2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{x(n+x)+y^2}{n[(n+x)^2+y^2]} \right] \quad (14)$$

$$Im(\Psi(x+iy)) = y \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{(n+x)^2+y^2} \right] \quad (15)$$

Proof. This lemma can be established using [Definition 7](#). The proof is written as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
\Psi(s) &= \Psi(x+iy) \\
&= -\gamma - \frac{1}{s} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{s}{n[n+s]} \right] \\
&= -\gamma - \frac{1}{x+iy} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{x+iy}{n[n+x+iy]} \right] \\
&= -\gamma - \left[\frac{x-iy}{x^2+y^2} \right] + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{(x+iy)(n+x-iy)}{n[(n+x)^2+y^2]} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we get the following results (which establishes this lemma).

$$Re(\Psi(x+iy)) = -\gamma - \frac{x}{x^2+y^2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{x(n+x)+y^2}{n[(n+x)^2+y^2]} \right]$$

$$Im(\Psi(x+iy)) = y \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{(n+x)^2+y^2} \right]$$

□

Lemma 7. $\int_0^{0.5} [Re(\Psi(\frac{s}{2})) - Re(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2}))] dx > 0$

Proof. We know that the Digamma function is a logarithmic derivative of the Gamma function. Therefore, integrating it should restore the natural log of the Gamma function.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_0^{0.5} \left[\operatorname{Re} \left(\Psi \left(\frac{s}{2} \right) \right) - \operatorname{Re} \left(\Psi \left(\frac{1-s}{2} \right) \right) \right] dx \\
&= \int_0^{0.5} \left[2 \frac{\partial}{\partial \left(\frac{x}{2} \right)} \left[\operatorname{Re} \left(\ln \left(\Gamma \left(\frac{s}{2} \right) \right) \right) \right] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{x}{2} \right] \right] + 2 \frac{\partial}{\partial \left(\frac{1-x}{2} \right)} \left[\operatorname{Re} \left(\ln \left(\Gamma \left(\frac{1-s}{2} \right) \right) \right) \right] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{1-x}{2} \right] \right] \right] dx \\
&= 2 \left[\operatorname{Re} \left(\ln \left(\Gamma \left(\frac{s}{2} \right) \Gamma \left(\frac{1-s}{2} \right) \right) \right) \right]_0^{0.5} \\
&= \left[\ln \left(\left| \Gamma \left(\frac{s}{2} \right) \Gamma \left(\frac{1-s}{2} \right) \right|^2 \right) \right]_0^{0.5} \\
&= \left[\ln \left(\left| \Gamma \left(0.25 + \frac{iy}{2} \right) \Gamma \left(0.25 - \frac{iy}{2} \right) \right|^2 \right) \right] - \left[\ln \left(\left| \Gamma \left(\frac{iy}{2} \right) \Gamma \left(0.5 - \frac{iy}{2} \right) \right|^2 \right) \right] \\
&= \left[\ln \left(\left| \Gamma \left(0.25 + \frac{iy}{2} \right) \right|^4 \right) \right] - \left[\ln \left(\left| \Gamma \left(\frac{iy}{2} \right) \right|^2 \left| \Gamma \left(0.5 - \frac{iy}{2} \right) \right|^2 \right) \right] \\
&= \left[\ln \left(\frac{\left| \Gamma \left(0.25 + \frac{iy}{2} \right) \right|^4}{\left| \Gamma \left(\frac{iy}{2} \right) \right|^2 \left| \Gamma \left(0.5 - \frac{iy}{2} \right) \right|^2} \right) \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

Let $A(0.5) = \left| \Gamma \left(0.25 + \frac{iy}{2} \right) \right|^4$ & $A(0) = \left| \Gamma \left(\frac{iy}{2} \right) \right|^2 \left| \Gamma \left(0.5 - \frac{iy}{2} \right) \right|^2$. To prove that the resultant natural log is positive, we need to prove that $A(0.5) > A(0)$. To proceed with that, let us evaluate $A(0)$ first (using [Definition 4](#) & the identity $m\Gamma(m) = \Gamma(1+m)$).

$$\begin{aligned}
A(0) &= \left[\Gamma \left(0.5 + \frac{iy}{2} \right) \Gamma \left(0.5 - \frac{iy}{2} \right) \right] \left[\Gamma \left(\frac{iy}{2} \right) \Gamma \left(-\frac{iy}{2} \right) \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{\pi}{\sin \left(\pi \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{iy}{2} \right) \right)} \right] \left[\left[\Gamma \left(\frac{iy}{2} \right) \right] \left[\frac{\Gamma \left(1 - \frac{iy}{2} \right)}{\frac{-iy}{2}} \right] \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{\pi}{\cos \left(\frac{i\pi y}{2} \right)} \right] \left[\left[\Gamma \left(\frac{iy}{2} \right) \right] \left[\frac{\pi}{\sin \left(\frac{i\pi y}{2} \right) \Gamma \left(\frac{iy}{2} \right) \left[\frac{-iy}{2} \right]} \right] \right] \\
&= \frac{2\pi^2}{y \cosh \left(\frac{\pi y}{2} \right) \sinh \left(\frac{\pi y}{2} \right) [-i^2]} \\
&= \frac{4\pi^2}{y \sinh(\pi y)}
\end{aligned}$$

Now, in order to prove that $\ln \left(\frac{A(0.5)}{A(0)} \right)$ does not have any root point when $y > 14$, we need to prove that $\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\ln \left(\frac{A(0.5)}{A(0)} \right) \right] < 0 \forall y > 14$ & $\lim_{y \rightarrow \infty} \left[\ln \left(\frac{A(0.5)}{A(0)} \right) \right] = 0$. The proof is as follows (using [Lemma 6](#), the hyperbolic cotangent infinite sum $\coth(y) = \frac{1}{y} +$

$2y \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{y^2 + n^2 \pi^2} \right]$ (Olver et. al. 2010 [3], Section 4.36.3), and the Laplace Transform $\frac{y}{k^2 + y^2} = \int_0^{\infty} [e^{-kt} \sin(yt)] dt$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\ln \left(\frac{A(0.5)}{A(0)} \right) \right] &= \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\ln \left(\left| \Gamma \left(0.25 + \frac{iy}{2} \right) \right|^4 \left[\frac{y \sinh(\pi y)}{4\pi^2} \right] \right) \right] \\
&= \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[2 \ln \left(\left| \Gamma \left(1 - 0.75 - \frac{iy}{2} \right) \right|^2 \right) + \ln(y) + \ln(\sinh(\pi y)) - \ln(4\pi^2) \right] \\
&= \left[2 \operatorname{Im} \left(\Psi \left(1 - 0.75 - \frac{iy}{2} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{y} + \pi \coth(\pi y) \right] \\
&= \left[2 \left[\frac{-y}{2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{(n+0.25)^2 + \frac{y^2}{4}} \right] \right] + \frac{1}{y} + \pi \left[\frac{1}{\pi y} + 2\pi y \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{\pi^2 y^2 + n^2 \pi^2} \right] \right] \right] \\
&= \left[- \left[4y \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{(2n+0.5)^2 + y^2} \right] \right] + \frac{2}{y} + \left[2y \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{y^2 + n^2} \right] \right] \right] \\
&= \left[- \left[4y \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{(2n+0.5)^2 + y^2} \right] \right] + \left[2y \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{y^2 + n^2} \right] \right] \right] \\
&= \left[- \left[4 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[\int_0^{\infty} [e^{-(2n+0.5)t} \sin(yt)] dt \right] \right] + \left[2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[\int_0^{\infty} [e^{-nt} \sin(yt)] dt \right] \right] \right] \\
&= \left[- \left[4 \int_0^{\infty} \left[\left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} e^{-(2n+0.5)t} \right] \sin(yt) \right] dt \right] + \left[2 \int_0^{\infty} \left[\left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} e^{-nt} \right] \sin(yt) \right] dt \right] \right] \\
&= \left[- \left[4 \int_0^{\infty} \left[\frac{e^{-0.5t} \sin(yt)}{1 - e^{-2t}} \right] dt \right] + \left[2 \int_0^{\infty} \left[\frac{\sin(yt)}{1 - e^{-t}} \right] dt \right] \right] \\
&= \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left[\left[\frac{2(1 + e^{-t}) - 4e^{-0.5t}}{1 - e^{-2t}} \right] \sin(yt) \right] dt \right] \\
&= \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left[\left[\frac{2(1 - e^{-0.5t})^2}{(1 + e^{-t})(1 + e^{-0.5t})(1 - e^{-0.5t})} \right] \sin(yt) \right] dt \right] \\
&= \left[\int_0^{\infty} \left[\left[\frac{2(1 - e^{-0.5t})}{(1 + e^{-t})(1 + e^{-0.5t})} \right] \sin(yt) \right] dt \right]
\end{aligned}$$

Let $f(t) = \frac{2(1 - e^{-0.5t})}{(1 + e^{-t})(1 + e^{-0.5t})}$. Using the quotient rule, we can establish that $f(t)$ is an increasing function. Therefore, by using [Lemma 2](#), we can conclude that $\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\ln \left(\frac{A(0.5)}{A(0)} \right) \right] < 0$.

We now have to prove that $\lim_{y \rightarrow \infty} \left[\ln \left(\frac{A(0.5)}{A(0)} \right) \right] = 0$. The proof is as follows (using the asymptotic equivalence relation $|\Gamma(s)| \sim \sqrt{2\pi} |y|^{x-0.5} e^{-\frac{\pi|y|}{2}}$ (Olver et. al. 2010 [3], Section 5.11.9). It can be used as the equivalence relation approaches the same asymptote line as the Gamma function, as y approaches infinity).

$$\begin{aligned}
\lim_{y \rightarrow \infty} \left[\ln \left(\frac{A(0.5)}{A(0)} \right) \right] &= \lim_{y \rightarrow \infty} \left[\ln \left(\left[\left| \Gamma \left(0.25 + \frac{iy}{2} \right) \right|^4 \right] \left[\frac{y \sinh(\pi y)}{4\pi^2} \right] \right) \right] \\
&= \lim_{y \rightarrow \infty} \left[\ln \left(y \left[4\pi^2 \left[\frac{y}{2} \right]^{4(0.25)-2} e^{-[2\pi] \left[\frac{y}{2} \right]} \right] \left[\frac{e^{\pi y} - e^{-\pi y}}{8\pi^2} \right] \right) \right] \\
&= \lim_{y \rightarrow \infty} \left[\ln \left([8\pi^2] \left[\frac{1 - e^{-2\pi y}}{8\pi^2} \right] \right) \right] \\
&= \left[\ln \left([8\pi^2] \left[\frac{1}{8\pi^2} \right] \right) \right] \\
&= [\ln(1)] \\
&= 0
\end{aligned}$$

As we have proved all necessary conditions to prove that $\ln \left(\left[\left| \Gamma \left(0.25 + \frac{iy}{2} \right) \right|^4 \right] \left[\frac{y \sinh(\pi y)}{4\pi^2} \right] \right)$ doesn't have any roots when $y > 14$ and also that it is strictly decreasing with respect to y (when $y > 14$), we can conclude with certainty that [Equation 16](#) is greater than zero. Hence the theorem is proved. \square

Lemma 8. *The partial derivative of $Re(\Psi(x + iy))$ with respect to y is greater than zero (and the partial derivative of $Im(\Psi(x + iy))$ with respect to x is lesser than zero in the x -interval $(0,1)$).*

Proof. The proof is built using [Lemma 6](#) as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial}{\partial y} [Re(\Psi(x + iy))] &= \left[\frac{2xy}{[x^2 + y^2]^2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{[[n[(n+x)^2 + y^2]] [2y] - [x(n+x) + y^2] [2ny]]}{n^2 [(n+x)^2 + y^2]^2} \right] \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{2xy}{[x^2 + y^2]^2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{[2ny][n^2 + x^2 + y^2 + 2xn - xn - x^2 - y^2]}{n^2 [(n+x)^2 + y^2]^2} \right] \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{2xy}{[x^2 + y^2]^2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{[2y][x+n]}{[(n+x)^2 + y^2]^2} \right] \right] \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{[2y][x+n]}{[(n+x)^2 + y^2]^2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

The infinite sum is always positive. Therefore, the partial derivative $\frac{\partial}{\partial y} [Re(\Psi(x + iy))]$ is always positive.

According to Cauchy-Riemann Equations, $\frac{\partial}{\partial y} [Re(\Psi(x + iy))] = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [Im(\Psi(x + iy))]$.

Therefore, we get the following relation (which proves the second half of this lemma).

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} [\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(x + iy))] = - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{[2y][x+n]}{[(n+x)^2 + y^2]^2} \right]$$

□

Lemma 9. $\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(x + iy))$ and $\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(1 - x - iy))$ are always greater than one (and 2.63884) whenever x belongs to $(0,1)$ and $y \geq 14$.

Proof. With the partial derivative of the real part of the Digamma function with respect to y (from Lemma 8), we have established that $\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(x + iy))$ is always increasing with respect to y . With the following plot, whenever $y \geq 14$ and x belongs to $(0,1)$, we can confirm that $\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(x + iy)) > 1$ (thereby making it greater than $\frac{\pi}{4}$).

FIGURE 1. A plot of $\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(x + 14i))$ (Generated with: WolframCloud).

As $\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(x + 14i))$ is an increasing function with respect to y , we can be certain that $\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(x + 14i))$ cannot drop below the values of this graph (which acts as a lower bound) whenever $y \geq 14$ and x belongs to $(0,1)$. Therefore, $\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(x + 14i)) > 1$ (and 2.63884) whenever $y \geq 14$ and x belongs to $(0,1)$. $\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(1 - x - 14i))$ is just a reflection of $\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(x + 14i))$ about $x = 0.5$ (when x belongs to $(0,1)$ (since $\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(x + 14i))$ is symmetric with respect to the y -axis)). Therefore, our conclusion is true for $\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(1 - x - 14i))$ as well.

□

Lemma 10. $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{x}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right] < 0 \quad \forall x \in (0, 0.5) \ \& \ y > 28.$

Proof. The proof is as follows (using the product rule, chain rule, [Lemma 5](#), & [Lemma 9](#)).

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{\pi^x \ln(\pi)}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2 \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))}{\left[|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2\right]^2} \right] - \left[-\frac{\pi^{1-x} \ln(\pi)}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} + \frac{\pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2}))}{\left[|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2\right]^2} \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{\pi^x [\ln(\pi) - \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))]}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] + \left[\frac{\pi^{1-x} [\ln(\pi) - \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2}))]}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right] \\
&< 0
\end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

□

Lemma 11. $f(x, y)$ is defined to be equal to the square of the modulus of two non-zero factors (within the critical strip) of the Riemann-Zeta Analytic Continuation functional equation (from [Definition 8](#)).

$$f(x, y) = \left[\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right] [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] \tag{18}$$

Proof. This lemma can be established from [Lemma 1](#)

□

Lemma 12. $\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}$ (from [Lemma 11](#)), is defined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} &= - \left[\left[\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right] [2 [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] [\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(1-x-iy))]] \right] \\
&\quad + \left[\left[\pi \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) \right] [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Proof. The proof is a self-explanatory application of the product and chain rule of derivatives, and the usage of [Lemma 5](#). □

Lemma 13. $\forall x \in (0, 1)$ & $y \geq 14$, $\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} < 0$

Proof. If the absolute value of the first term of the RHS (Right Hand Side) of [Lemma 12](#) is equal to the absolute value of its second term, then after the application of the sine double angle identity, we get the following equation.

$$\left[\left[\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right] [\operatorname{Re}(\Psi(1-x-iy))] \right] = \left[\left[\frac{\pi}{4} \right] [\sin(\pi x)] \right]$$

The previously mentioned equation makes it very clear that the LHS (Left Hand Side) is always greater than $\frac{\pi}{4}$ whenever x belongs to $(0, 1)$ (and whenever $y \geq 14$, which can be established by just looking at the lower bound plot of [Figure 1](#)) and the RHS is always less than $\frac{\pi}{4}$ in the same x -interval. As both terms can't be equal, and the first term of [Lemma 12](#) is always greater than the second term, [Lemma 12](#) is always negative. Therefore, this lemma is true. □

Lemma 14. The square of the modulus of the Zeta function (from [Definition 8](#)) is as follows.

$$|\zeta(s)|^2 = \left[\frac{(2\pi)^{2x}}{\pi^2} \right] \left[\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right] [|\Gamma(1-s)|^2] [|\zeta(1-s)|^2] \tag{20}$$

Proof. The proof can be explained using [Definition 3](#) and [Lemma 1](#). \square

Lemma 15. *If $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [f(x, y)(2\pi)^{2x}] = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\pi^2]$, we get the following equation.*

$$2 [\ln (2\pi) f(x, y)] + \left[\frac{\pi}{2} [\sin (\pi x)] [|\Gamma (1-x-iy)|^2] - [2 [f(x, y)] [Re (\Psi (1-x-iy))]] \right] = 0 \quad (21)$$

Proof. By expanding the LHS and the RHS of the problem statement (using [Lemma 12](#)), we get the following equation.

$$\begin{aligned} &+ [2(2\pi)^{2x} \ln (2\pi) f(x, y)] + (2\pi)^{2x} \left[\pi \sin \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) \cos \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) \right] [|\Gamma (1-x-iy)|^2] \\ &- (2\pi)^{2x} \left[\sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} \right) + \sinh^2 \left(\frac{\pi y}{2} \right) \right] [2 [|\Gamma (1-x-iy)|^2] [Re (\Psi (1-x-iy))]] = 0 \end{aligned}$$

By simplifying it further, we get the following equation.

$$2 [\ln (2\pi) f(x, y)] + \left[\frac{\pi}{2} [\sin (\pi x)] [|\Gamma (1-x-iy)|^2] - [2 [f(x, y)] [Re (\Psi (1-x-iy))]] \right] = 0 \quad \square$$

Lemma 16. $\forall x \in (0, 1) \ \& \ y \geq 14, \ |\Gamma (1-x-iy)|^2 < 1$

Proof. From [Lemma 5](#), we get the following equation.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} [|\Gamma (1-x-iy)|^2] = 2 [|\Gamma (1-x-iy)|^2] [Im (\Psi (1-x-iy))]$$

By the usage of [Lemma 6](#), we get the following equation.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} [|\Gamma (1-x-iy)|^2] = -2 [|\Gamma (1-x-iy)|^2] \left[y \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{(n+1-x)^2 + y^2} \right] \right]$$

Therefore, we can understand that the square of the modulus of the Gamma function is always decreasing with respect to y . Therefore, this function should have values that are lower than $|\Gamma (1-x-14i)|^2$ whenever $y \geq 14$ and x belongs to $(0,1)$. The following plot thus establishes this lemma.

FIGURE 2. A plot displaying the minuscule values of $|\Gamma (1-x-14i)|^2$ within our given constraints (Generated with: WolframCloud).

□

Lemma 17. $\forall x \in (0, 1) \ \& \ y \geq 14$, the following inequality is always true.

$$2 [\ln(2\pi) f(x, y)] + \frac{\pi}{2} [\sin(\pi x)] [|\Gamma(1 - x - iy)|^2] < 2 [f(x, y)] [Re(\Psi(1 - x - iy))] \quad (22)$$

Proof. Our inequality can be written as follows.

$$[\ln(2\pi) f(x, y)] + \frac{\pi}{4} [\sin(\pi x)] [|\Gamma(1 - x - iy)|^2] < [f(x, y)] [Re(\Psi(1 - x - iy))]$$

By simple comparison, we can understand that $\ln(2\pi) f(x, y) < f(x, y) Re(\Psi(1 - x - iy))$ (since $f(x, y) > \frac{\pi}{2}$, which will be proven in [Proposition 2](#), and $Re(\Psi(1 - x - iy)) > 2.6$ (according to [Lemma 9](#)) and $\frac{\pi}{4} [\sin(\pi x)] [|\Gamma(1 - x - iy)|^2] < 1$ (since [Lemma 16](#) makes $\frac{\pi}{4}$ the upper bound of the LHS of this inequality). 1.8 times a function that is greater than 1, added with a small decimal number around 0.7 is definitely lesser than 2.6 times the same function. A proof has been mentioned here if it is necessary (where $c = \frac{\pi}{4} [\sin(\pi x)] [|\Gamma(1 - x - iy)|^2]$ is a parameter that belongs to the interval $(0, \frac{\pi}{4})$).

$$c < [f(x, y)] [Re(\Psi(1 - x - iy)) - \ln(2\pi)]$$

It can be re-written as follows.

$$\frac{\pi [\sin(\pi x)] [|\Gamma(1 - x - iy)|^2]}{4 [Re(\Psi(1 - x - iy)) - \ln(2\pi)]} < \left[\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right] [|\Gamma(1 - x - iy)|^2]$$

After cancellation, we get the following inequality.

$$\frac{\pi [\sin(\pi x)]}{4 [Re(\Psi(1 - x - iy)) - \ln(2\pi)]} < \left[\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right]$$

Within our given constraints, since the numerator of the LHS of the previous inequality is always lesser than its denominator, and the RHS of the same inequality is always greater than 1, this lemma is thus true. □

Corollary 1. $\forall x \in (0, 1) \ \& \ y \geq 14$, $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [f(x, y)(2\pi)^{2x}] < 0$

Proof. This corollary can be established from the previous lemma ([Lemma 17](#)). This lemma also establishes that $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [f(x, y)(2\pi)^{2x}]$ cannot turn to zero within our given constraints either (since a derivative not being equal to zero implies that there's no extremum within that interval, and that the function can't be a constant in that interval — thereby eliminating the possibility of an extremum, as well as a constant function of this product within our given constraints). □

4. PROPOSITIONS AND THEOREMS

The first two propositions in this section seem to lead to a known result. But my analytic methods establish the same as well. As these two propositions led to the theorem, I wanted to include these in my paper.

Proposition 1. All non-zero equal points $|\zeta(x + iy)|^2 = |\zeta(1 - x - iy)|^2$ of the Zeta function satisfy the following condition.

$$\left[\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right] [|\Gamma(1 - x - iy)|^2] = \frac{\pi^2}{(2\pi)^{2x}} \quad (23)$$

Proof. The proof is based on the symmetry of the Riemann-Xi function with respect to the x-axis about the plane $x = 0.5$ (from [Definition 2](#)). The proof is as follows.

$$|\xi(x + iy)|^2 = |\xi(1 - x - iy)|^2$$

We can now substitute the Riemann-Xi function (from [Lemma 3](#)).

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{[x^2 + y^2] [(1-x)^2 + y^2] \left[\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{x+iy}{2}\right) \right|^2 \right] [|\zeta(x+iy)|^2]}{4\pi^x} \right] \\ &= \left[\frac{[x^2 + y^2] [(1-x)^2 + y^2] \left[\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{1-x-iy}{2}\right) \right|^2 \right] [|\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2]}{4\pi^{1-x}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

We now cancel the common factors of the LHS and the RHS. After the cancellation, we get the following equation.

$$\left[\frac{\left[\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{x+iy}{2}\right) \right|^2 \right] [|\zeta(x+iy)|^2]}{4\pi^x} \right] = \left[\frac{\left[\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{1-x-iy}{2}\right) \right|^2 \right] [|\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2]}{4\pi^{1-x}} \right]$$

We are now replacing $|\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2$ with $|\zeta(x+iy)|^2$ in the LHS (by assuming that $|\zeta(x+iy)|^2 = |\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2 \neq 0$). After the substitution, we get the following equation.

$$\left[\frac{\left[\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{x+iy}{2}\right) \right|^2 \right] [|\zeta(x+iy)|^2]}{4\pi^x} \right] = \left[\frac{\left[\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{1-x-iy}{2}\right) \right|^2 \right] [|\zeta(x+iy)|^2]}{4\pi^{1-x}} \right]$$

We are now dividing both sides with $|\zeta(x+iy)|^2$. The following equation obtained after the division is thus valid at all non-zero points of the Zeta function.

$$\left[\frac{\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{x+iy}{2}\right) \right|^2}{4\pi^x} \right] = \left[\frac{\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{1-x-iy}{2}\right) \right|^2}{4\pi^{1-x}} \right]$$

Upon further simplification, we get the following equation.

$$\left[\frac{\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{x+iy}{2}\right) \right|^2}{\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{1-x-iy}{2}\right) \right|^2} \right] = \pi^{2x-1}$$

By using Euler's Reflection Formula (from [Definition 4](#)) in the numerator of the LHS & Legendre's Duplication Formula (from [Definition 5](#)) in the denominator of the LHS, we get the following equation.

$$\left| \left[\frac{\pi}{\left[\sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \right] \left[\Gamma\left(1 - \frac{s}{2}\right) \right]} \right] \left[\frac{\left[2^{\frac{2(1-s)}{2}-1} \right] \left[\Gamma\left(\frac{1-s}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right) \right]}{\left[\Gamma\left(2\left(\frac{1-s}{2}\right)\right) \right] \left[\pi^{0.5} \right]} \right] \right|^2 = \pi^{2x-1}$$

$\Gamma\left(\frac{1-s}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right) = \Gamma\left(1 - \frac{s}{2}\right)$. Therefore, we can cancel it from the numerator and denominator of the LHS. And after further general simplifications (using [Definition 3](#)), we get the following

equation.

$$\left[\left[\frac{\pi^{2-1}}{|\sin(\frac{\pi s}{2})|^2} \right] \left[\frac{2^{-2x}}{|\Gamma(1-s)|^2} \right] \right] = \pi^{2x-1}$$

Upon further simplification by using [Lemma 1](#), we get the following equation (which is our current theorem).

$$\left[\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right] [|\Gamma(1-x-iy)|^2] = \frac{\pi^2}{(2\pi)^{2x}}$$

□

Proposition 2. *Proposition 1 can be true only when $x = 0.5$ (within the critical strip).*

Proof. There're at least two methods to prove this statement when $x = 0.5$. The first method is to use [Lemma 12](#). When $x = 0.5$, $s = 0.5 + iy$, and $|\zeta(x+iy)|^2 = |\zeta(1-x-iy)|^2$. Therefore, [Lemma 14](#) becomes the following statement (which is our current theorem when $x = 0.5$).

$$\left[\frac{1}{2} + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right] \left[\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2} - iy\right) \right|^2 \right] = \frac{\pi}{2}$$

The second method is as follows (from [Definition 4](#)).

$$|\Gamma(0.5 + iy)| |\Gamma(0.5 - iy)| = \frac{\pi}{|\sin(\pi(0.5 + iy))|}$$

This equation leads to the following statement.

$$\begin{aligned} |\Gamma(0.5 + iy)|^2 &= \left[\frac{\pi}{|\cos(i\pi y)|} \right] \\ &= \left[\frac{\pi}{\cosh(\pi y)} \right] \end{aligned}$$

Now, we need to focus on the other half.

$$\begin{aligned} \left[0.5 + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right] &= \left[0.5 - \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right] \\ &= \left[0.5 - 0.5 + \frac{\cos(i\pi y)}{2} \right] \\ &= \left[\frac{\cosh(\pi y)}{2} \right] \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, by multiplying $|\Gamma(0.5 + iy)|^2$ and $\left[0.5 + \sinh^2\left(\frac{\pi y}{2}\right) \right]$, we can prove that the theorem is true when $x = 0.5$.

Now comes the question of whether it is true only when $x = 0.5$ (when x belongs to $(0, 0.5)$ for the purposes of this calculation). If, there exists any other point where this theorem is true, the LHS curve of this equation would then have to create a minimum (with respect to x) to definitely pass through the RHS curve when $x = 0.5$. It can be better understood with the next plot.

FIGURE 3. A plot of the LHS curve of [Proposition 1](#) when $y = 14$ and $y = 21$ and the RHS curve of [Proposition 1](#) (Generated with: WolframCloud).

Now it should be understandable why there needs to be a minimum / extremum for the LHS curve to pass through (or meet) the RHS curve in the x-interval $(0,0.5)$ and pass through the RHS curve (or meet it) again when $x = 0.5$.

By using [Lemma 13](#), we can understand that it is not possible for the LHS curve to contain a minimum / extremum within the x-interval $(0,1)$ and when $y \geq 14$ (since the function is always decreasing within the given constraints). That just leaves us with two other possibilities.

- 1) Partial coincidence of the LHS curve with the RHS curve for all x-values in the interval $[k,1-k]$ (for any k value in the interval $(0,0.5)$ - since
 - 1) the LHS curve is decreasing,
 - 2) the LHS curve has to meet the RHS curve when $x = 0.5$ and when $x = 1 - k$ and,
 - 3) the LHS curve cannot go below the RHS curve (at least in the interval $(k,1-k)$ — due to the absence of an extremum)),
- 2) Complete coincidence of the LHS with the RHS curve (for all x-values in the x-interval $(0,1)$).

If either partial or complete coincidence is true, it would mean that the tangent line becomes the same for both the LHS and the RHS curve of this theorem after the particular point k (at least upto when $x = 1 - k$ or when $x = 1$ (basically in the interval $(k,1-k)$ or $(k,0.5)$ or both)). It can be proved that [Lemma 15](#) (a modified version of the same argument) can never be true (at least when x belongs to $(0,0.5)$) using [Lemma 17](#).

Therefore, partial coincidence or complete coincidence cannot be true. This theorem (which can be established with [Corollary 1](#) as well), is thus true only when $x = 0.5$. \square

Theorem 1. *The Riemann Hypothesis is true.*

Proof. The proof can be established from [Lemma 14](#) (which is the functional equation of the Zeta function) and [Corollary 1](#) as follows (and we also consider

$f(x, y) = [\sin^2(\frac{\pi x}{2}) + \sinh^2(\frac{\pi y}{2})] [|\Gamma(1 - x - iy)|^2]$ (as mentioned in [Lemma 11](#))).

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(x + iy)|^2] \\ &= \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\left[\frac{(2\pi)^{2x}}{\pi^2} f(x, y) \right] \right] [|\zeta(1 - x - iy)|^2] + \left[\left[\frac{(2\pi)^{2x}}{\pi^2} f(x, y) \right] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(1 - x - iy)|^2] \right] \right] \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Now, from [Corollary 1](#), we know that the first term of the RHS is always negative when x belongs to $(0, 0.5)$. So, if the second term is negative for the entire domain of x belonging to $(0, 0.5)$ as well, it would support Riemann Hypothesis.

Suppose the second term is negative and the LHS is positive. Now, the addition of two negative numbers in the RHS would not lead to a positive number. This is a clear case of Mathematical contradiction.

There is one more case we need to address. The LHS would be positive in that case and the second term of the RHS, would be positive in that case. To handle that case, let us re-visit the functional equation in the following format (where $|k(s)|^2 = |k(1 - s)|^2$).

$$\frac{|\zeta(s)|^2}{|\zeta(1 - s)|^2} = \frac{\pi^x |k(s)|^2}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \quad (25)$$

Now, from the standalone closed-form expression above ([Equation 25](#)), we obtain the following equations.

$$\ln(|\zeta(s)|^2) - \ln(|\zeta(1 - s)|^2) = (2x - 1) \ln(\pi) + \ln \left[\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{1 - s}{2}\right) \right|^2 \right] - \ln \left[\left| \Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \right|^2 \right] \quad (26)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\ln(|\zeta(s)|^2)] - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\ln(|\zeta(1 - s)|^2)] &= \frac{[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2]] [|\zeta(1 - s)|^2] - [\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(1 - s)|^2]] [|\zeta(s)|^2]}{[|\zeta(s)|^2] [|\zeta(1 - s)|^2]} \\ &= 2 \ln(\pi) - \left[Re \left[\Psi\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \right] + Re \left[\Psi\left(\frac{1 - s}{2}\right) \right] \right] \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

$$|\zeta(s)|^2 = \frac{\pi^x |k(s)|^2}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \quad (28)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\ln(|\zeta(s)|^2)] = \ln(\pi) + \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [k(s)]^2}{|k(s)|^2} - Re \left[\Psi\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \right] \quad (29)$$

$$|\zeta(1 - s)|^2 = \frac{\pi^{1-x} |k(1 - s)|^2}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \quad (30)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\ln (|\zeta (1-s)|^2)] = -\ln (\pi) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{|k(1-s)|^2}{|k(1-s)|^2} \right] + \operatorname{Re} \left[\Psi \left(\frac{1-s}{2} \right) \right] \quad (31)$$

$$[|\zeta(s)|^2] - [|\zeta(1-s)|^2] = \left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right] [|k(s)|^2] \quad (32)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2 - |\zeta(1-s)|^2] \\ &= \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right] \right] [|k(s)|^2] + \left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|k(s)|^2] \right] \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

Equation 32 is a new function which shares all the complex root points of $|\zeta(s)|^2$. It is also skew-symmetric (odd) about the critical line $x = 0.5$. This is a function which is greater than zero when x belongs to $(0, 0.5)$ (as $|\zeta(s)|^2$ is a product of $|\zeta(1-s)|^2$ and a factor (Lemma 14) which is greater than 1 (when x belongs to $(0,0.5)$). Any positive number multiplied with a number greater than 1 would produce a result that is greater than the original number. Therefore $[|\zeta(s)|^2] - [|\zeta(1-s)|^2] \geq 0$). Extremum points would thus be present at complex roots whose real part is not equal to 0.5. Therefore, if a complex root off the critical line exists, it would lead to one of the three following possibilities.

FIGURE 4. Possibility 1: A plot of $[|\zeta(s)|^2] - [|\zeta(1-s)|^2]$ (Equation 32) and $|k(s)|^2$ where from the left root, $|k(s)|^2$ reached the first maximum faster than $[|\zeta(s)|^2] - [|\zeta(1-s)|^2]$ (Generated with: WolframCloud).

FIGURE 5. Possibility 2: A plot of $[|\zeta(s)|^2] - [|\zeta(1-s)|^2]$ (Equation 32) and $|k(s)|^2$ where from the left root, $[|\zeta(s)|^2] - [|\zeta(1-s)|^2]$ reached the first maximum faster than $|k(s)|^2$ (Generated with: WolframCloud).

FIGURE 6. Possibility 3: A plot of $[|\zeta(s)|^2] - [|\zeta(1-s)|^2]$ (Equation 32) and $|k(s)|^2$ where both attain a maximum at the same point.

Let us look at Equation 33 to eliminate possibility 1. In it, the first term of the RHS is always negative when x belongs to $(0, 0.5)$ (from Lemma 10). As for this factor $\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2}$ in the second term, it is positive as we have already established that $[|\zeta(s)|^2] - [|\zeta(1-s)|^2] > 0$. This result is thus a consequence of Equation 32. By using Lemma 7 & $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|k(s)|^2] = 0$ in Equation 33, we can establish that possibility 1 cannot exist (since the RHS is now negative and the LHS is positive, which is a contradiction). Now that we have eliminated possibility 1, let us evaluate possibility 2.

If possibility 2 exists, the following equations would be true.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2 - |\zeta(1-s)|^2] = 0 \quad (34)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2] = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(1-s)|^2] \quad (35)$$

By using [Equation 35](#) in [Equation 27](#), we get the following steps.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\ln(|\zeta(s)|^2)] - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\ln(|\zeta(1-s)|^2)] &= \frac{[[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2]] [|\zeta(1-s)|^2] - [\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(1-s)|^2]] [|\zeta(s)|^2]}{[|\zeta(s)|^2] [|\zeta(1-s)|^2]} \\ &= \frac{[[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2]] [|\zeta(1-s)|^2 - |\zeta(s)|^2]}{[|\zeta(s)|^2] [|\zeta(1-s)|^2]} \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

From these steps, we can conclude that $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2] > 0$ (since $[|\zeta(1-s)|^2 - |\zeta(s)|^2] < 0$ when x belongs to $(0, 0.5)$, and the result of [Equation 36](#) is supposed to be negative). Now the question becomes whether $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2]$ can be greater than zero. If $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2] > 0$, then $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\ln(|\zeta(s)|^2)] > 0$. Let us now use [Equation 34](#), [Equation 33](#), [Equation 31](#), [Equation 29](#), & [Lemma 10](#) to check if that's true.

$$0 = \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right] \right] [k(s)|^2] + \left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [k(s)|^2] \right] \quad (37)$$

$$- \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right] \right] [k(s)|^2] = \left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [k(s)|^2] \right] \quad (38)$$

$$- \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right]}{\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2}} \right] = \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [k(s)|^2]}{|k(s)|^2} \right] \quad (39)$$

$$- \left[\frac{\left[\frac{\pi^x [\ln(\pi) - \text{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))]}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] + \left[\frac{\pi^{1-x} [\ln(\pi) - \text{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2}))]}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right]}{\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2}} \right] = \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [k(s)|^2]}{|k(s)|^2} \right] \quad (40)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\ln (|\zeta (1-s)|^2)] &= -\ln (\pi) - \left[\frac{\left[\frac{\pi^x [\ln (\pi) - \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))]}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] + \left[\frac{\pi^{1-x} [\ln (\pi) - \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2}))]}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right]}{\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2}} \right] + \operatorname{Re} \left[\Psi \left(\frac{1-s}{2} \right) \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{\left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] [-2 \ln (\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2})) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))]}{\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2}} \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{41}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\ln (|\zeta (s)|^2)] &= \ln (\pi) - \left[\frac{\left[\frac{\pi^x [\ln (\pi) - \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))]}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] + \left[\frac{\pi^{1-x} [\ln (\pi) - \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2}))]}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right]}{\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2}} \right] - \operatorname{Re} \left[\Psi \left(\frac{s}{2} \right) \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{\left[\frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right] [-2 \ln (\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2})) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))]}{\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2}} \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{42}$$

Let us now define the following function (from [Equation 28](#) & [Equation 30](#)).

$$\frac{|\zeta (s)|^2 |\zeta (1-s)|^2}{|\zeta (s)|^2 - |\zeta (1-s)|^2} = \frac{\pi |k(s)|^2}{\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 - \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \tag{43}$$

[Equation 43](#) describes a special function which is odd about the critical line (just like the function $|\zeta (s)|^2 - |\zeta (1-s)|^2$ in the above plots). This function has poles on the critical line (except at the roots on the critical line, which can be deduced by a standard application of Bernoulli's rule (with respect to x) on indeterminate forms of the type $\frac{0}{0}$). This function does not have poles on non-critical line complex roots either (which can be deduced by just substituting zero instead of $|k(s)|^2$, as the denominator turns zero only on the critical line). This is indeed an interesting function which retains all the characteristics of how there're stationary points with respect to x at zeroes (just like $|\zeta (s)|^2 - |\zeta (1-s)|^2$). Let us now use this function to analyze our previous results.

Let us now differentiate the LHS of [Equation 43](#) with respect to x and use the condition $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta (s)|^2] = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta (1-s)|^2]$.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{|\zeta(s)|^2 |\zeta(1-s)|^2}{|\zeta(s)|^2 - |\zeta(1-s)|^2} \\
&= \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2] \right] \left[\frac{|\zeta(s)|^2 + |\zeta(1-s)|^2}{|\zeta(s)|^2 - |\zeta(1-s)|^2} \right] + \left[\frac{|\zeta(s)|^2 |\zeta(1-s)|^2}{|\zeta(s)|^2 - |\zeta(1-s)|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2] - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(1-s)|^2] \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2] \right] \left[\frac{|\zeta(s)|^2 + |\zeta(1-s)|^2}{|\zeta(s)|^2 - |\zeta(1-s)|^2} \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{44}$$

Let us now differentiate the RHS of [Equation 43](#) with respect to x (using [Equation 37](#)).

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2] \right] \left[\frac{|\zeta(s)|^2 + |\zeta(1-s)|^2}{|\zeta(s)|^2 - |\zeta(1-s)|^2} \right] \\
&= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{\pi |k(s)|^2}{\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 - \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] \\
&= - \frac{\pi \left[\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 [\ln(\pi) - \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2}))] - \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2 [-\ln(\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))] \right] |k(s)|^2}{\left[\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 - \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2 \right]^2} \\
&\quad + \left[\frac{\pi |k(s)|^2}{\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 - \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2]}{|k(s)|^2} \right] \\
&= \frac{\pi \left[|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2 |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 \right] \left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} [-\ln(\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2}))] + \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} [-\ln(\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))] \right] |k(s)|^2}{\left[\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 - \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2 \right]^2} \\
&\quad + \left[\frac{\pi |k(s)|^2}{\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 - \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2]}{|k(s)|^2} \right] \\
&= \frac{\pi \left[|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2 |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 \right] |k(s)|^2}{\left[|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2 |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 \right] \left[\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 - \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2 \right]} \left[\left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2]}{|k(s)|^2} \right] \right] \\
&\quad + \left[\frac{\pi |k(s)|^2}{\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 - \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2]}{|k(s)|^2} \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{2\pi |k(s)|^2}{\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 - \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2]}{|k(s)|^2} \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{45}$$

Therefore, we get the following equation.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2]}{|\zeta(s)|^2 - |\zeta(1-s)|^2} \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{2\pi |k(s)|^2}{\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 - \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|k(s)|^2]}{|k(s)|^2} \right] \left[\frac{1}{|\zeta(s)|^2 + |\zeta(1-s)|^2} \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{2\pi |k(s)|^2}{\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 - \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|k(s)|^2]}{|k(s)|^2} \right] \left[\frac{1}{\left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} + \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right] [|k(s)|^2]} \right] \quad (46) \\
&= \left[\frac{[2\pi] \left[|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2 |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 \right]}{\pi^{2x} |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^4 - \pi^{2-2x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^4} \right] \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|k(s)|^2]}{|k(s)|^2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we get the following equation.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2] = \left[\frac{[2\pi] \left[|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2 |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 \right] [|\zeta(s)|^2 - |\zeta(1-s)|^2]}{\pi^{2x} |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^4 - \pi^{2-2x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^4} \right] \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|k(s)|^2]}{|k(s)|^2} \right] \quad (47)$$

Let us now substitute [Equation 47](#) in [Equation 41](#) and obtain an equation (by using the reflection formula in [Lemma 14](#)).

$$\begin{aligned}
& |\zeta(1-s)|^2 \\
&= \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(1-s)|^2] \right] \left[\frac{\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2}}{\left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] [-2 \ln(\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2})) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))]} \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(1-s)|^2] \right] \left[\frac{\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 - \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2 |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 \left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] [-2 \ln(\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2})) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))]} \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{[2\pi] [|\zeta(s)|^2 - |\zeta(1-s)|^2]}{\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 + \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|k(s)|^2]}{|k(s)|^2} \right] \left[\frac{1}{\left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] [-2 \ln(\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2})) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))]} \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{[2\pi] [|\zeta(s)|^2 - |\zeta(1-s)|^2]}{\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 + \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|k(s)|^2]}{|k(s)|^2} \right] \left[\frac{1}{\left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] [-2 \ln(\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2})) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))]} \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{[2\pi] |\zeta(1-s)|^2}{\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 + \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|k(s)|^2]}{|k(s)|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\frac{\pi^{2x-1} |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} - 1}{\left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] [-2 \ln(\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2})) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))]} \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{[2\pi] |\zeta(1-s)|^2}{\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 + \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|k(s)|^2]}{|k(s)|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\frac{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2}{\pi^{1-x}} - \frac{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2}{\pi^x}}{[-2 \ln(\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2})) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))]} \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{2 |\zeta(1-s)|^2}{\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 + \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|k(s)|^2]}{|k(s)|^2} \right] \left[\frac{\pi^x |\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2 - \pi^{1-x} |\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2}{[-2 \ln(\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2})) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))]} \right] \\
&= \left[\frac{2 |\zeta(1-s)|^2}{\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} + \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2}} \right] \left[\frac{\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} [-\ln(\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))] + \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} [-\ln(\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2}))]}{[-2 \ln(\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2})) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))]} \right] \tag{48}
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we get the following equation.

$$1 = 2 \left[\frac{\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} [-\ln(\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))] + \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} [-\ln(\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2}))]}{\left[\frac{\pi^x}{|\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})|^2} + \frac{\pi^{1-x}}{|\Gamma(\frac{1-s}{2})|^2} \right] [-2 \ln(\pi) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{1-s}{2})) + \operatorname{Re}(\Psi(\frac{s}{2}))]} \right] \tag{49}$$

Equation 49 can be true only when $x = 0.5$ (Since the difference between the Numerator (including the coefficient of 2), and the Denominator is positive within our given constraints of $0 < x < 0.5$ and $y > 28$, implying that the only possible solution in this half region of

the critical strip, exists on the critical line). It would imply the existence of a maximum in $|\zeta(s)|^2$ when $x = 0.5$, and thereby, the existence of Equation 35. Since this is a contradiction (as the maximum of Figure 5 is not on the critical line), we can conclude that possibility 2 cannot exist.

We can also prove this contradiction using Equation 24 for good measure. Substitution of zero in its LHS and the second term of the RHS lead to a scenario where zero is equal to a negative number. We also already proved that $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [|\zeta(s)|^2] > 0$ using Equation 36. We thus obtain multiple contradictions from multiple methods. Therefore, this possibility cannot exist.

Let us now move onto Possibility 3. By using Equation 33, and by substituting the conditions necessary for possibility 3 (where LHS=0 and the second term of the RHS is also equal to zero), we easily arrive at a contradiction of zero being equal to a negative number. Therefore, possibility 3 cannot exist either.

Since maximum / minimum points are an essential condition for complex roots to exist off the critical line, we can establish that there are no complex roots off the critical line.

In short, the four / six conditions (including zeroes) are as follows.

TABLE 1. All relevant combinations of the pair

Sl. No.	Sign of $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\zeta(x + iy) ^2]$	Sign of $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\zeta(1 - x - iy) ^2]$	Possibility when x belongs to $(0, 0.5)$
1	-	-	Possible
2	-	+	Possible
3	-	0	Possible
4	+	-	Impossible
5	+	+	Impossible
6	+	0	Impossible

Therefore, $[|\zeta(x + iy)|^2]$ is thus strictly decreasing with respect to x when x belongs to $(0, 0.5)$ & $y > 14$. If the modulus is strictly decreasing in that interval, and happens to have a root point whose real part is not equal to 0.5, it would lead to the existence of negative results for the modulus function. But the modulus of any complex function is strictly non-negative. The Zeta function thus can't have complex roots whose real part is not equal to 0.5. Therefore, the Riemann Hypothesis (Riemann 1859 [1]) is true!

□

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